

Cold-associated injuries in Antarctica: a brief discussion on ‘polar thigh’

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1. Background

In 2022, almost one hundred and seven years after it was lost to pack ice, Sir Ernest Shackleton’s ship *Endurance*

was discovered in the Weddell Sea. Shackleton’s exploits in one of the harshest environments on earth is an epic story of survival and solid leadership, his name becoming essentially synonymous with the spirit of endurance.¹⁻³ The inherent risk of extended polar travel from the extreme cold are perhaps best summarised by the explorer himself, forewarning potential companions of embarking “without the prospect of any speedy return, and with reasonable probability of no return at all”,⁴ the underlying sentiment of which continues to be relevant today.

Navigating across in alpine glacier at the northern edge of the Rocky Mountains, Canada

In the years since, fascination with polar travel has continued. Ongoing scientific activity in Antarctica has global significance and as such is protected under the Antarctic Treaty, with key activities ranging from monitoring of climate change to serving as an earth analogue for space travel.⁵⁻⁶ For those drawn to the challenge, explorers, endurance athletes and adventurers continue to seek to test themselves in ever more daring journeys. While advances in communications, travel, nutrition, and the technology behind personnel

equipment and clothing have undoubtedly improved the safety profile since the days of Shackleton, considerable risk remains. Sudden changes in inclement weather conditions, momentary lapses in self-administration or failure of kit designed to protect against the extreme cold can all result in serious cold injuries with potential limb or life-threatening consequences. Cold injury broadly refers to conditions from hypothermia to a series of freezing such as frostbite and non-freezing cold injuries such as pernio/chilblains affecting skin and soft-tissues,⁷⁻⁸ all of which have been described in detail from accounts of Antarctic expeditions of the heroic age.⁹

The available literature on cold injuries remains limited. A recent British military case series highlights a change in presenting symptoms for non-freezing cold injuries since those described during the World Wars, and is a useful reminder that such injuries can occur following even short periods of exposure to the cold and are not limited to polar travel.¹⁰ In contrast, literature describing cold-associated injuries such as ‘polar thigh’ are virtually non-existent. A pubmed search for example using the search terms ‘arctic’, ‘antarctic’, ‘polar’, ‘thigh’ and/or ‘injury’ was unable to identify any peer-reviewed literature. The following brief discussion aims to provide some context to the previous articles in this edition of *Exploration Revealed* and provide a short introduction to this rare but potentially significant risk of polar travel.¹¹

2. Polar thigh

In the absence of peer-reviewed research, the best available information on polar thigh is perhaps limited to expert opinion, being discussed most fully in Auerbach’s *Wilderness Medicine* where it is considered an issue specific to polar skiing expeditions.¹² It is described there as the development of an “erythematous and frequently urticarial rash”¹² that most often affects the anterior thigh. While strongly associated with exposure to

extreme cold environments, expert opinion from management of the limited number of cases is that the constant abrasion from overlying materials in the context of cold exposure are likely to be key drivers of injury.¹² This is reflected by reports of polar thigh almost exclusively in those undertaking long-distance arduous polar journeys and while this is in keeping with the authors personal experience, the level of available research at present is observational.¹¹ While available data is considerably scarce, recent publicly available cases have seemed to be reported among women undertaking prolonged expeditions in Antarctica,¹³⁻¹⁵ Whether this reflects mechanical or immunometabolism factors that may be a higher risk in women or is a biased observation due to so few cases is unclear and would require formal research to explore further.

Accepted prevention measures include the use of a silk base layer and an insulated down skirt. Use of emollient creams or aloe vera gels to help reduce friction have also been recommended; aloe vera has the advantage of being a potent anti-prostaglandin.¹² Once a rash is realised, meticulous adjustments to clothing to reduce abrasion is paramount while some researchers have suggested there may be benefit in use of topical corticosteroid creams.¹² If early preventative measures are ineffective and abrasion continues then blistering and frank ulceration can develop which may require medical repatriation and review by a plastic surgeon.¹²⁻¹⁵ Decision for repatriation may be dependent on many factors and should follow informed discussion between the individual and their medical support (Figure 1). Once ulceration occurs steroid creams should be avoided, with limited evidence for benefit and delay to healing a recognised potential side-effects.¹⁶ Suitable dressings, for example a low-adherent, sterile, paraffin open weave gauze have been advised instead.¹² Wound healing is likely to take several

months even in uncomplicated cases (see reference 11 in this edition of Exploration Revealed for a thorough discussion on the development of a case of polar thigh and its potential psychological and long-term impact on the expeditioner), and may result in permanent scarring.

Perhaps surprisingly, infection rarely occurs and antibiotics are not routinely indicated.¹² Expert consensus among other authors on antibiotic use in cold injury in general highlight a lack of evidence for routine use of antibiotics but highlight their potential role in severe injury or where there are signs of emerging cellulitis or sepsis.¹⁷ Additionally, an opportunity to swab lesions prior to any antibiotics for microscopy, culture and sensitivities may prove invaluable should any surgical intervention be

“It is a very personal and contextual decision whether to continue with polar thigh. Personally, I am happy with my decision to continue to ski for a further 39 days, despite the management my thighs needed for four months on my return. I now have scars on both thighs, but no decrease in functionality and my scars act as a reminder of my challenging journey and human achievement.”

Figure 1. A personal account of managing with polar thigh while on expedition to the South Pole from Paula Reid.

required further down the line. Where ulceration has occurred however, individuals should remain vigilante for emerging signs of infection including spreading erythema, swelling, pain and pus with or without fever. If infection develops, given the location of injury, complicated recovery process, and risk of developing sepsis in a remote location urgent medical advice should be sought. In this circumstance broad spectrum antibiotics to cover both common skin gram positive organisms (such as *Staphylococcus aureus*) and gut gram negative organisms (such as *E.coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Citrobacter spp.*) may be indicated and should follow individualised medical advice. In this circumstance, an antibiotic such

Camped at the base of the Hardangerjøkulen

as amoxicillin-clavulanic acid may be a suitable initial empiric choice. On return to the UK advice should be sought from specialist centres (for example, the Institute of Naval Medicine for uniformed personnel or expert authors with experience of managing cases of polar thigh as cited here)¹² with advice from microbiology prior to any treatment for infection.

3. Summary

While it remains unclear, polar thigh is thought to be an injury that occurs following constant mechanical abrasion while skiing in extreme cold environments. Prevention efforts focus on measures to reduce friction from clothing or equipment. Injuries can develop to cause severe ulceration, risking the need

for medical evacuation. Literature is considerably limited and further reporting on successful preventative measures and clinical outcomes could be helpful to further delineate this risk to those planning prolonged polar travel. In the meantime those intending to travel should familiarise themselves with the polar medicine chapter of Auerbach's Wilderness Medicine. ■

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Declarations

Authors' contributions

RHM is currently working as a doctor providing medical support to the British Antarctic Survey out of at Rothera Research Station. PR is a polar expeditioner with personnel experience of managing polar thigh. SJCP is a British Army medical officer, currently undertaking specialist training in infectious diseases and

microbiology. SJCP drafted the initial manuscript. All authors contributed significantly to revising this for submission. All authors agreed on the final version for submission to the journal.

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Ethical approval and consent to participate

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Potential conflicts of interests

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